

LIFE AND ACTIVITY OF THE GREAT POET AND SCIENTIST

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Abstract: This article is the life of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, activity, rich and colorful creative-scientific heritage and to the poet by our state the attention given to youth education of the poet's works today and is devoted to the importance of non-existence in his scientific life.

Key words: Thinker, great poet, encyclopedist, statesman Umar Sheikh Mirza, International Public Foundation named after Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur, Third Renaissance, Boburnoma.

One of the unique figures who left an indelible mark in world history is Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is a great poet, encyclopedist, statesman and a skilled commander is known and famous all over the world. His incomparable scientific and creative heritage not only of our national culture and literary-aesthetic thinking of our people unique in its formation, but also in the history of world literature, science and statehood has a place.

The life of Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur during the period of independence and comprehensive study of his activities, his works in our country and wide-scale work on promotion in foreign countries was carried out. In particular, the poet's birthday is February 14 every year throughout our country is celebrated as a holiday of literature and science. Philology many researches in the field, national and international scientific conferences is held regularly.

In the following years, in the cities of Tashkent and Andijan, Bobur Mirza that huge statues were installed in the city of Andijan, where he was born and raised International public foundation named after Babur and "Babur and the World" under its management Culture" Book Museum, "Babur and the World" The organization of the magazine is recognized as a major event in our cultural life done.

Our country is entering a new stage of national development - the Third Today, when we are entering the renaissance era and fundamental changes are taking place in all aspects of our lives, we must remember the priceless legacy of Babur Mirza. in-depth study and popularization are becoming more important.

The national and universal nature of the works of our great ancestor, his to increase the intellectual and spiritual potential of our young generation, our children on this basis, it is important to educate the creators of New Uzbekistan taking into

account the place and influence, the scientific and creative heritage of Babur Mirza further study and promotion in our country and internationally intended. Including:

Ministry of Culture and Tourism, Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation, Academy of Sciences, Union of Writers, Republic of Spirituality and Center for Enlightenment, Babur International Public Fund and the public 540th birthday of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in 2023 the proposal to widely celebrate the anniversary was approved. Uzbekistan The President of the Republic of January 25, 2023 "Great poet and scientist, 540 of the birth of the famous statesman Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur 2023- year 3 - February 84-8-0-Q/23 Decision of the Surkhandarya region hokimiyati to many scientific researches about Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur in our region the way was opened.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's scientific and creative heritage, statehood and scientific at the international level in order to study the activities of generals conducting researches and publishing their results, new scientific, artistic journalism decisions on the creation of works to the relevance of the article serves.

METHODS. The generally accepted methods in the article are objectivity, historical analysis, comparative logic analysis, based on the principles of chronological order, Alisher Navoi His life and work will be covered on the basis of historical-scientific and internet sources.

RESULTS. It should be noted that Zahiriddin in our country Monuments and monuments related to the name of Muhammad Babur, including repair of memorial complexes and beautification of their territories and Manuscripts, ancient books, works of art and restoration of other cultural assets at a reliable level creation of necessary conditions for storage was included in the plan. Also Babur The people who gave birth to such classic people will never be humiliated. inevitably attains bliss. As we turn the pages of history, the world culture of the Uzbek people his great contribution to the treasury, his spirituality from the distant past to the world It is obvious that it has become known and popular. The name of the nation when it comes to the glorified scholars, his talent, intelligence, Zahiriddin Muhammed, a poet with a complicated fate and an open spiritual world Babur attracts more attention to himself. He is a statesman, a poet, a soldier, a scientist, historian, literary critic, linguist, and at the same time a cheerful person as having many wonderful qualities.

Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur was born on February 14, 1483 in Andijan, Ferghana. He was born in the family of Umar Shaykh Mirza, the ruler of the ulus. In this period In Central Asia and Khorasan, between different governors and relatives struggle for ownership of a large state built by his great-grandfather Amir Temur was

extremely tense. Love for literature and the beauty of nature from a young age Babur's father learned science from experienced teachers in the palace. But Babur's innocent and carefree youth did not last long 1494 from his father in 1506 and the mother who gave birth to him died. Babur was orphaned by his father at the age of 12 after his stay, he was promoted to the governor of Fergana ulus. Babur's pen his brother Jahangir Mirza, uncle Sultan for the throne of Andijan in exchange for a sword Ahmad Mirza against his uncle Sultan Muhammad and other rivals had to fight. In 1504, Shyboni Khan captured Andijan After entering, Babur headed south and established his own in Kabul created the power, this incident affected Babur very badly, because The place where he was born and raised is in a foreign land, separated from the place where his navel blood was spilled how hard it was to be a king.

But Babur returned to Central Asia in 1505-1515 tried everything, but these efforts did not yield any results. After in order to further strengthen his position, during the years 1519-1525 He fought several battles to conquer India. April 1525 In Panipat, Babur defeated Delhi Sultan Ibrahim Lodi with an army of 12,000 defeated his army of 100 thousand warriors and elephants and in March 1527 Babur had the upper hand in the battle with Rano Sango, the governor of Chitaro. After these great victories, Babur founded the Babur dynasty in India Babur did not live long after these events. On December 26, 1530 Died in Agra. He is in the Nurafshonda garden on the left bank of the Jamna river was buried. Later, according to his will, his children took his governor to Kabul come and be buried. However, in a short time, "Babur is political in Hundistan stabilization of the environment, integration of Indian lands, cities beautified, sponsored the proper implementation of trade issues. Facilitate the writing of Babur, eliminate various reading defects In order to achieve this, he discovered a new script, Baburi's letter. Babur India after taking over, he issued just laws, abolished the jizya (extortion tax), forbids the burning of the dead husband's living wife with the corpse. Gardens creation of architectural monuments, libraries, Caravanserai, construction, especially during the period of his sons on a large scale spread. The wise son of India, the great statesman Jawahir Lal Nehru describes the cultural environment in the Babur state as follows: "Babur After coming to India, there were many changes and new developments Art, fresh air, architecture, life, culture, etc and the fields are connected to each other. The Baburites are widespread in world history long years is a dynasty that ruled for 332 years. Bangladesh today A person who visited the capital city of Dhaka entered the historical museum "Lalbagh-Kala". Clothes, military weapons belonging to Babur and Baburi, Ustad Aliquli stone cannons, rifles, armor, swords and shields made the people of that time People of

India and Bangladesh who watched in the dress of their time A witness of how much respect and consideration was given to Babur and Baburi we will be Zahridin Muhammad Babur's kingdom in historical books In addition to his leadership and scholarly talent, he also knew jurisprudence perfectlyis brought. In Nisari's work "Muzakkiri akhbob" (memoir of beloved people). There are such words about Babur: In another treatise on the issues of jurisprudence stated that the writer is a symbol of his wisdom. Turkish and There are some good poems in Persian, and the name of that jurisprudence treatise is "Mubayyin". Babur Mirza selected the most important Islamic sciences in his work "Mubayyin". A religious scholar, a jurist, the tax system of that time, the law of tax collection rules, how much tax to collect from whom according to Sharia and other issues explained in the poem. Son of Asar Zahiruddin Muhammad Babur Ascribed to Humayun in 928 AH during the Indian Campaigns (1521 AD) was classified in the poetic way. Babur ruled for five years and died on December 26, 1530. In this short time, the health of the owner of the great kingdom deteriorated despite his progress, he managed to do great positive things.

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